

TOURISM TERMS AND THEIR SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of tourism terms, their types and semantic peculiarities, types of the terms and their meaning on the material of the English language.

Keywords: term, tourism terms, semantic properties, terminology, term system, borrow term.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola turizm atamalarini, ularning turlari va semantik xususiyatlarini, atamalarning turlari va ingliz tili materialidagi ma'nosini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: termin, turizm atamalari, semantik xususiyatlari, terminologiyasi, termin tizimi, o'zlashtirilgan termin.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена изучению туристских терминов, их видов и семантических особенностей, типов терминов и их значения на материале английского языка.

Ключевые слова: термин, термины туризма, смысловые свойства, терминология, терминологическая система, термин заимствования

In linguistics differentiate some basic groups such lexicology, phonology and grammar. In the same way these branches are also subdivided into groups.

Lexicology consists of following:

- Semasiology
- Etymology
- Terminology
- Lexicography

In terminology scholars studied the term and its historical development, its usage, semantic features and others. In generally, there are four types of terms. They are : opaque terms, transparent terms, iconic terms, eponymous terms. Opaque terms, where such no attempt in apparent (e.g. verb). Transparent terms, where the term attempts to give some indication of the meaning of the concept

(e.g countable). Iconic terms where the term reflects (partly, or at least) the form of the referent (e.g -ing form). Eponymous terms – a subset of the third type will be described, and combinations will also be considered.

The tendency to borrow terms from English terminological systems can be traced in most world's developed languages. Applying a common language facilitates international communication and encourages information exchange. Selected linguists stress the leading role of English as the language of international business, economics, commerce, politics, science, etc. in the modern world. Some researchers believe that uncritical borrowing of vocabulary, cultural and behaviour patterns leads to a loss of cultural diversity, while others suppose that the increased influence of the English language on other languages has favourably affected the progress of the post-modern world. With reference to the English language leading role in the world, R.Phillipson and some other English-language researchers resort to the term "language imperialism", presupposing dominance, conditioned by establishment and constant support of structural and cultural inequality between English and other languages. R.Phillipson suggests that "the ideologies and structures which are used to legitimate, effectuate and reproduce an unequal division of power and resources (both material and nonmaterial) between groups which are defined on the basis of their language (i.e., of their mother tongue)". Referring to linguistic imperialism, R.Phillipson clarifies: "an essential constituent of imperialism as a global phenomenon involves structural relations between rich and poor countries in a world characterized by inequality and injustice". Thus, the interaction between contacting languages can be considered both negative and positive.

According to D. S. Lotte, the synonymous terms are divided into absolute and relative. By absolute synonyms, he understands the synonyms, the content of which is identical, while with relative synonyms the meaning concurrence is only partial. He also points out that the existence of two or more terms to define one concept eventually leads to the fact that one of these terms semantic structure can either get narrower or expand, or can even refer to a completely different concept. This results in absolute synonyms becoming relative. [2]

Tourism terminology is an important section of the term system of any language. This is explained by the fact that the sphere of tourism occupies an important place and plays a significant role in the life and activity of each person. Tourism terminology is characterized by a wide variety of applications in comparison with other terminological systems. The problems that have been actively developing in recent decades which are related to the peculiarity of specific languages have posed a set of questions for researchers that are reflected in the study of the

characteristics and typologies of multi-structured languages. The relevance of the study is determined by the growth of intercultural relations, the role of the language of tourism in the modern communicative process, as well as the insufficient knowledge of word-formation, morphological, semantic and functional characteristics of tourist terminology. Language, as a system, has enough laws and means of education of new concepts. They may be found in special vocabulary and require nomination. One of the common means of nominating tourist terms is the use of multi-valued common language words in a special touristic field. Many scientists have definitely argued that the term is a lexico-nominative language unit that corresponds to the concept of a special professional sphere, for example tourism. There are three points of view:

1. Tourist terms have that lexical meaning which they mean;
2. Tourist terms have a lexical meaning and it is the concept;
3. Such terms coincide with the concept and have no lexical meaning . Speaking about the semantic structure of the word-term, you shouldn't forget about its structure and internal form. The method of decomposition of the tourist term into constituent semantic components in order to simulate its semantics is fully justified. The same tourist term can be defined differently. It can be included in different systems.

An elementary semantic concept is formed in the process of verbal transfer of knowledge on the basis of the text informativeness of the term. Various types of informativeness provide for the presence of certain patterns of realization of the semantic potential of the term. If the sign information content is transmitted based on the implementation of semantic features that are identified and definitional and classification is based on features that are differentiated, then signs relevant to a specific communicative situation are actualized in the texts. The best way to form a term is to use commonly used words that are based on both the generalized nature of the word and its meaning creating opportunities.[1]

Tourist terms differ from common words in that they have a definition that reveals the most essential features of special concepts. Another way to create terms is specialization of the meaning of a commonly used word. It arises as a result of various kinds of transition of its basic meaning, metaphor, metonymy, etc. It should be noted that tourist terms that designate the same object or phenomenon may have the on conceptual integrity as the main independent layer of the vocabulary of the language. The term's ambiguity in the process of its formation, development and functioning is natural. The same form can adapt to the designation of various objects and perform different functions. The analysis

of lexical and semantic connections of tourist terms shows that these connections can be internally systemic and intersystem. Thus, within the systemic semantic phenomenon, the polysemy of the same term within the same terminological system is considered. Systemic and structural features are the main criteria for determining a tourist term in English language system. In one system of language there are no absolutely identical signs, therefore, there are no absolute synonyms, because in one system of concepts there are no two or more different signs that would be called the same term. Thus, the development of tourism led to the emergence of numerous English borrowings to refer to concepts that were previously absent in reality. Along with this, there is a tendency to use Anglo-Americanisms instead of the existing words in the receptor language to give habitual objects and phenomena 'western character', prestige. Some travel companies use literal translation of terms, others use Anglo-American vocabulary along with Russian. Most borrowings of the term 'tourism' pass through two stages of adaptation to the language system: 'entry' into the receiving language (phonetic and graphic level) and mastering the borrowed term by the receiving language (semantic level). So, the study of the structural and semantic relations between the terms implies the continuity of two plans that are interconnected: a stable invariant semantic component of the paradigmatic plan of the language system and the expression of variable components from the syntagmatic plan of speech, which determine, respectively, different meanings of the use of the word term.

In the modern English language as a whole and in scientific terminology, in particular, there is a tendency to intensify English language borrowings for a number of extra and intralingual reasons. The dynamic development of the English-speaking tourist business has led to the emergence of borrowed terminology into the English language on the one hand, and on the other hand, as a result, there appeared a language vacuum in relation to the nomination of new and previously unknown concepts. The analysis of the current state of English tourism terminology conducted in the study proves the opinion by linguists that this terminology system is still being developed and rationalized, as the new English-language tourism terms have not yet been fully mastered in the other language. In this regard, the issue of a more comprehensive and detailed lexicographical consolidation of terms in this area is especially acute.

If we interpret the special knowledge in the most generalized way, being the basic and highly informative units of scientific speech, the terms should provide assistance in scientific and special communication. Tourism terms are found in written and oral forms of communication, so, knowing them as well as being able

to apply them to the context properly can guarantee successful interaction in various communicative situations.

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